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EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHER CERTIFICATION IN IMPROVING SERVICE PROFESSIONAL SERVICE IN MADRASAH ALIYAH STATE OF JAMBI PROVINCE

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to find out the factors that resulted in the inability of the effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services in the Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province, how effective the certification of teachers in the Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province, how teacher professional services in the Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province, and how the effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province. The research approach used is a qualitative approach where data collection techniques are carried out by means of observation, interviews, and documentation.

This study results in findings that the effectiveness of teacher certification in the Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province has not been able to optimally improve teacher professional services due to inconsistent recruitment procedures for teacher certification candidates, weak implementation of government regulations on government employees

discipline, the absence of regulations that bind certified teachers, and the actualization of certified teacher actualization. The effectiveness of teacher certification has not been implemented properly due to the operational guidelines and technical guidelines for teacher certification which only lead to the fulfillment of administrative obligations and have not touched on the impact and results of the teacher professional allowance. Teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province prioritize the fulfillment of non-substantive aspects. The effectiveness of teacher certification in the improvement of professional care services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province is more pragmatic. So that certified teachers are more concerned with meeting economic needs rather than updating in the teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Effectiveness; Certification; Teachers; Education Services.

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1. Introduction

Improvement of teacher professionalism through education and training which became known as PLPG (Teacher Education and Training) which is held by several universities so that later teachers have formal licenses from the government, and therefore every teacher who has received an educator certificate has the right to obtain teacher professional allowance. Teacher education and training is one form of government attention in increasing the professionalism of teaching staff which is the implementation of the body of the 1945 Constitution which reads "educating the life of the nation". In addition, teacher certification is a concrete effort by the government to improve the quality of education in various dimensions and scope of national education, by providing the 4 competencies that must be possessed by a teacher. The four competencies are personal competence, personality competence, professional competence and social competence. The certification is carried out with portfolio assessment, as well as education and training for those who do not pass the portfolio.¹

Michael G. Fullan was quoted by Suyanto and Djihad Hisham as saying that "*educational change depends on what teachers do and think...*".² Asnandar Abubakar in his research gave an initial assumption that improving teacher quality will be coupled with improving teacher welfare so that it is expected to improve the quality of learning and the quality of education in a sustainable manner. But then he concluded that the use of certification allowances did not have a significant impact on improving the quality of education services in madrasahs. But on the contrary, the indicators that appear are that the use of certification allowances is more dominantly intended for consumptive purposes.³ Hastarini Dwi Atmawati revealed in her research that although teachers who have received certification allowances always try to improve their competence and try to produce new innovations in education, education services have not been able to be presented properly and perfectly.⁴ The birth of the Law on Teachers and Lecturers through Law No. 14 of 2005 legally formally provides a concrete explanation that teachers and lecturers become professionals who are highly expected to improve the quality of education in Indonesia.⁵

The main concept promoted by Mukhtar and Iskandar is the renewal of education in totality, for this reason, he offers a trilogy of educational renewal innovations, namely: management innovation, organizational innovation, and policy innovation.⁶ Decision making and determination of the provision of professional allowances for teachers is the managerial authority of the principal / madrasah, especially in relation to improving education services in various educational institutions. For this reason, serious attention must be paid by policy makers and prioritizes the interests of the education community. Paul Rrowler explained that an important point in a policy is the specification of principles and actions must be followed, designed, formulated and implemented in an effort to achieve the expected goals.⁷

¹Muhamad Muhammad, *Kiat Menjadi Guru Profesional*, (Yogyakarta: Ar-Ruzz Media, 2008), hlm. 97

²<http://www.psb-psma.org/content/blog/peran-kepala-sekolah-dalam-meningkatkan-kompetensi-guru>

³Asnandar Abubakar, Dampak Sertifikasi Guru Terhadap Kualitas Pendidikan Pada Madrasah Aliyah di Kota Kendari, *Jurnal "Al Qalam"* Volume 21 Nomor 1 Juni 2015, hlm. 126

⁴Hastarini Dwi Atmawati, Investasi Sumber Daya Manusia Melalui Pendidikan, *Jurnal Dinamika Pembangunan*, vol. 2 Nomor 2, agustus 2014, hlm. 273

⁵M. Sirozi, *Politik Pendidikan*, (Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada, 2005), hlm. 37

⁶H. Mukhtar dan Iskandar, *Orientasi Baru Supervisi Pendidikan*, (Jakarta: Gaung Persada Press, 2009), hlm. 1

⁷Paul Trowler, *Education Policy*, (London and New York: Routledge, 2003), hlm. 95

Syaiful Sagala emphasized that improving the quality of education is obtained through two strategies, namely improving the quality of education that is academically oriented and improving the quality of education oriented to essential life skills included in inclusive, real and meaningful education.⁸ According to Shoimin, improving teacher quality coupled with improving teacher welfare is expected to improve the quality of learning and the quality of education in a sustainable manner.⁹ The expectation of the community for certified teachers is that they can provide good service quality through increasing teacher competence, both in the pedagogical, professional, personality, and social competency aspects.¹⁰

The improvement of education services in educational institutions as stated in the previous discussion is influenced by several factors, including individual factors (both principals / madrasas and teachers), organizational environmental factors, and policy factors related to the improvement of these services. According to A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara that with the existence of high integrity between the psychological and physical functions of a person, the individual has good self concentration and is the main capital in managing and utilizing his potential optimally in carrying out daily activities or activities, especially within the scope of educational institutions . In addition, a conducive organizational environment will have a direct and indirect impact on the service products produced. There is a clear job description description, adequate authority, challenging work targets, effective work communication patterns, harmonious working relationships, a dynamic work climate, career opportunities and relatively adequate work facilities, as well as sufficient financial benefits to provide support and good encouragement in improving services provided. ¹¹

Theoretically, the certification allowance given to teaching staff is able to improve the service products provided at various educational institutions. ¹² The allocation of government funds through certification allowances is one form of investment in the field of human resources. The purpose of providing the certification allowance is to increase the competency of teaching staff in providing optimal education services. Management of certification in an effort to improve education services in schools / madrasas in relation to human resources capital. Singodimejo was quoted by Edy Sutrisno that there are three main aspects that form a substantial foundation in ensuring one's productivity, namely: 1) aspects of workforce management capabilities, 2) aspects of labor efficiency, and 3) aspects of work environment conditions. Thus, the improvement of education services in addition to being influenced by adequate funding, also a good managerial aspect strongly supports the realization of good education services in accordance with the expectations and goals of education. ¹³

Some of the information that the authors gathered from a number of study results on the impact of certification on improving education services in schools / madrasas which later became the

⁸Syaiful Sagala, *Manajemen Strategik Dalam Peningkatan Mutu*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2007), hlm. 170

⁹Aris Shoimin, *Excellent Teacher: Meningkatkan Profesionalisme Guru Pasca Sertifikasi*, (Semarang: Dahara Prize, 2013), hlm. 79

¹⁰Jamil Suprihatiningrum, *Guru Profesional: Pedoman Kerja, Kualifikasi dan Kompetensi Guru*, (Yogyakarta: Ar Ruzz Media, 2013), hlm. 215

¹¹A.A. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara, *Evaluasi Kinerja SDM*, (PT. Refika Aditama, 2010), cet. Ke- 5, hlm. 16-17

¹²The World Bank, *Mentransformasi Tenaga Pendidikan Indonesia*, (Jakarta: Bank Dunia, 2011), vol. 2, hlm. 66

¹³Edy Sutrisno, *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, (Jakarta: Kencana, 2011), cet. Ke- 3, hlm. 100

grandtour of this research, including the results of evaluations conducted by the Indonesian government in collaboration with the World Bank. The results of the evaluation resulted in the finding that the certification allowance had resulted in several positive changes in teacher behavior. However, this change has not had a significant impact on improving student learning outcomes.¹⁴

Grandtour that the researchers conducted at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri (MAN) Jambi Province in this case was represented by three regions, namely the first at MAN 1 Bangko. The madrasah head provides information that government efforts in improving the quality of education through education services in schools / madrasahs have not been fully realized in line with expectations, it can be seen from several indicators including the low quality of madrasah graduates, low teacher innovation in learning activities teaching, and the competitiveness mentality of teachers has not been able to accommodate the development of science and technology. However, the provision of these allowances has been able to improve the welfare of teachers in various educational institutions marked by the improvement in the quality of their transportation facilities, such as the purchase of four-wheeled vehicles and other secondary needs which actually lead to the fulfillment of hedonic-patterned living needs. providing certification allowances, i.e. increasing scientific capacity and pedagogical skills to improve education services in schools / madrasahs.¹⁵

Further information researchers obtained from MAN 1 Kuala Tungkal, Tanjung Jabung Barat District, representatives of the western region of the study site. The madrasa head explained the implications of providing certification allowances for teachers on the quality of education services provided, namely the improvement in teacher welfare, which was marked by the ability of teachers to buy primary and secondary needs. The madrasah head also said that the majority of teachers prioritize meeting secondary needs rather than primary needs related to improving pedagogical qualifications and competencies.¹⁶

As for further information, namely in MAN 3, the City of Jambi represents the central region in the zoning of the study area. The madrasah head explained that the provision of certification allowances to teachers has not been fully able to improve education services. The main objective of providing certification allowances is almost deviated from the main objective, namely to improve the quality of education services, so that it has implications for the low quality and quality of education services in various educational institutions, both at national and regional levels.¹⁷

The main problem in this research is that there is an indication of misperception between the decision maker which in this case is the government through the Ministry of National Education with educational practitioners in various educational institutions. For this reason, the authors made unstructured observations in several Madrasah Aliyah in the city of Jambi to see a portrait of educational services provided by educators, especially those who have received certification allowances. In these observations, the authors get information that educators have not fully provided maximum educational services and have not made various innovations that can support their competencies in teaching and learning activities. On the contrary, the interesting thing that

¹⁴Bank Indonesia, Laporan Mingguan (Weekly Report), No. 73264, Oktober 2012, Sertifikasi Guru di Indonesia: Peningkatan Pendapatan atau Cara untuk Meningkatkan Pembelajaran, Jakarta, 2012, hlm. 1

¹⁵Wawancara dengan Nurzal J. Bakri, Kepala MAN 1 Sungai Penuh Kerinci. Sabtu, 21 Mei 2016

¹⁶Wawancara dengan Drs. H. Syarkawi, M.Pd, Kepala MAN 1 Kuala Tungkal Kab. Tanjung Jabung Barat. Kamis, 25 Agustus 2016

¹⁷Wawancara dengan Drs. M. Zakri K, M.Pd.I, Kepala MAN 3 Kota Jambi. Senin, 22 Agustus 2016

the writer needs to point out is that the improvement in welfare among the teaching staff is getting better which is marked by an increase in means of transportation. Chronologically, the writer can also point out that prior to the certification allowance, educators are more likely to use two-wheeled transportation, but after the certification allowance the number of four-wheeled vehicles has increased in various educational institutions. This can be used as an indication that the welfare of educators has increased from several previous periods. But ironically, it has not been accompanied by an increase in aspects of pedagogical competencies that have direct implications on education services.¹⁸

Seeing some of the phenomena of the use of certification allowances as stated in the previous discussion, the authors are very interested in examining more closely related to how the management of certification allowances in improving education services in schools / madrasas. This is because the main purpose of providing certification for educators is to increase their professionalism in educational activities comprehensively. To produce factual data from this study, the authors sought to present research with a focus of study on managing certification in increasing the effectiveness of education services in schools / madrasas.

2. Problem Formulation

The main problems mentioned above are then described in a number of problem formulations which later become a reference in the following discussion as follows: 1. Why is the effectiveness of teacher certification not yet able to improve teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province ?, 2. How is the effectiveness of teacher certification in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province, 3. What is the service of the teaching profession in Madrasah Aliyah Jambi Province Negeri ?, 4. What is the effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province?

3. Theory Study

3.1. Effectiveness

Effectiveness is a condition that affects an impressive thing, efficacy, business success, actions or things that apply. Sedarmayanti said that effectiveness is a measure that gives an idea of how far the target can be achieved.¹⁹ Supriyono said that effectiveness is the relationship between the output of a center of responsibility and the goals that must be achieved, the greater the contribution of the output produced to the value of achieving those targets, then the unit can be said to be effective too.²⁰ According to Yamit effectiveness is a measure that gives an idea of how far the goal is achieved, both in quality and time, its orientation to the output produced.²¹ McLeod in Azhar said the effectiveness of the meaning of information must be in accordance with the needs of users in supporting a business process, the information is presented in the right time and format

¹⁸Observasi, Selasa 13 September 2016

¹⁹Sedarmayanti, *Sumber Daya Manusia dan Produktivitas Kerja*, (Bandung: CV. Mandar Maju, 2009), hlm. 59

²⁰Supriyono, *Sistem Pengendalian Manajemen*, (Yogyakarta: BPFE, 2000), Edisi Pertama, hlm. 29

²¹Zulian Yamit, *Manajemen Produksi dan Operasi*, (Yogyakarta: Ekonisia, 2003), Edisi ke- 2, hlm. 14

so that it can be understood, consistent with the previous format, its contents in accordance with current needs and complete or in accordance with the needs and conditions.²²

Based on some of the information above, it can be explained that the relation of efficiency, effectiveness, quality and production that efficiency can be said to be a measure in comparing the use of inputs. Thus, the effectiveness measure for an organization or institution can be seen from the Input, Production Process, Results (output), and Productivity.²³ David Krech, Ricard S. Cruthfied and Egerton L. Ballachey cited Sudarwan Danim mentioned the effectiveness measure that is²⁴ 1. the number of results that can be issued, 2 levels of satisfaction obtained, 3. creative products, 4. intensity to be achieved.²⁵ Cambell cited by Richard M. Steers measures of effectiveness, namely: 1. quality; 2. productivity; 3. alertness; 4. efficiency; 5. income; 6. growth; 7. stability; 8. accident; 9. enthusiasm for work 10. motivated; 11. cohesiveness 12. flexibility. Richard M. Steers mentioned the factors supporting effectiveness, namely:²⁶ 1. Organizational Characteristics, organizational structure and technology can be seen that affect certain aspects of effectiveness, in various ways. 2. environmental characteristics, the success of organizational and environmental relations depends on three things, namely: (a) environmental conditions, (b) accuracy of perception, (c) level of organizational rationality. 3. the characteristics of workers or employees, the behavior of workers in the long run will facilitate or hinder the achievement of organizational goals.

3.2. Certification

Education certificates are given to teachers who have met the professional standards of the teacher. Professional teachers are an absolute prerequisite for creating quality education systems and practices.²⁷ Teacher certification can also be interpreted as a process of giving recognition that a person already has the competence to carry out education services in a particular education unit, after passing the competency test held by the certification body.²⁸

Explanation of the Republic of Indonesia's Ministry of Education and Culture Regulation Number 5 of 2012 concerning Certification of Teachers in Position in article 2 paragraph 1 that certification is implemented through a pattern; portfolio assessment, teacher professional education and training, direct teacher certification, or teacher professional education. And Government Regulation No. 74/2008 concerning Teachers article 4 paragraph 1 states that teacher certificates are obtained through professional education programs organized by tertiary institutions that have an accredited education personnel procurement program, both organized by the government and the community and determined by the government.

²²Mc Leod dalam Azhar Susanto, *Sistem Informasi Manajemen*, (Bandung: Lingga Jaya, 2007), hlm. 41

²³Sedarmayanti, *Op.Cit.*, hlm. 60

²⁴M Richard Steers, *Efektivitas Organisasi Perusahaan*, (Jakarta: Erlangga, 1985), hlm. 46-48

²⁵Sudarwan Danim, *Motivasi Kepemimpinan dan Efektivitas Kelompok*, (Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2012), hlm. 119-120

²⁶M Richard Steers, *Ibid.*, hlm. 209

²⁷Aris Shoimin, *68 Model Pembelajaran Inovatif dalam Kurikulum 2013*, (Yogyakarta: Ar-Ruzz Media, 2013), hlm. 81

²⁸E. Mulyasa, *Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah*, (Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya, 2012), hlm. 34-35

Improving teacher welfare through various government programs including the provision of certification allowances is an effort to improve the standard of living of education workers who have been marginalized. The results of teacher certification can be easily used to determine the appropriate amount of rewards given to each teacher. This is considering that the teacher who has the main task of teaching is a profession.

Jobs (professions) in Islam must be undertaken with sincerity. Although in reality the work is done for others, but the underlying intention is God's command. Devotion in Islam, in addition to humanity, is also done for God, so there is a transcendent element in the implementation of professions in Islam. The transcendent element can make the practice of profession in Islam a higher value of service than the practice of profession that is not based on faith in God.²⁹

3.3. Pengelolaan

Management or often called management in general is often associated with activities in the organization in the form of planning, organizing, controlling, directing, and controlling. The word management is adapted from the English word "management" with the root word "manage" which means taking care of, managing, implementing, managing and treating. While the word management means management, governance, and management.³⁰ Management in a special sense means to lead and leadership, the activities carried out to manage the institution or organization in the process of leading and carrying out leadership in the organization, where the person who leads the organization is called the manager.³¹

James H. Donnelly, et. Al defines management as a process carried out by one or more people to regulate activities through others to achieve goals that are not possible by one person alone.³² While James A.F. Stoner defines management as the process of planning, organizing, and using other organizational resources in order to achieve predetermined organizational goals.³³

G.R. Terry is safely quoted by A.M. Kadarman and Yusuf Udaya mean that management is an art of science. These two aspects are integrated in order to direct and influence others to carry out the leader's plan and achieve the goals according to the wishes of the organization's leaders, both broad and narrow.³⁴

Malayu S.P. Hasibuan in his book "Management: Basics, Understanding, and Problems", explains that management is the science and art of regulating the process of utilizing the energy and professionalism of others.³⁵ Meanwhile E. Mulyasa believes that management is often juxtaposed with the term administration. In this connection, there are three different views; first, interpret administration broader than management, namely management is the core of administration;

²⁹ Ahmad Tafsir, *Ilmu Pendidikan Perspektif Islam*, (Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya, 2010), hlm. 13

³⁰John M. Echols dan Hassan Shadily, *Kamus Inggris-Indonesia*, (Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2003), cet. Ke- 25, hlm. 372

³¹A.M. Kadarman dan Yusuf Udaya, *Pengantar Ilmu Manajemen*, (Jakarta: PT. Prenhallindo, 2001), cet. Ke- 5, hlm. 6

³²James H. Donnelly, et. Al, *Fundamental of Management*, (Texas: Business Publication, Inc, 1984), hlm. 35

³³James A.F. Stoner, *Management*, (New York: Prantice Hall International, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, 1982), hlm. 8

³⁴A.M. Kadarman dan Yusuf Udaya, hlm. 6

³⁵Malayu S.P. Hasibuan, *Manajemen Dasar, Pengertian dan Masalah*, (Jakarta: Gunung Agung, 1996), hlm. 2

second, see management broader than administration; and third, the view that management is identical with administration. Furthermore, according to him that management is defined the same as the word administration or management.³⁶

The word management in the view of Parker Follet (Daft and Steers, 1986) as quoted by Syaiful Sagala states that management as "the art of getting things one through people" or more broadly defined as the process of achieving goals through efficient utilization of human and material resources.³⁷ According to Frederick Winslow Taylor "management is knowing exactly what you want to do and then seeing that they do it in the best and cheapest way". (management is knowing exactly what you want to do, and you see that they do it in the best and cheapest way).³⁸

Harsoyo views management as a term derived from the word "manage" which means a series of efforts aimed at exploring and exploiting all potentials that are owned effectively and efficiently in order to achieve certain goals that have been previously planned.³⁹ Based on the explanation above, the author then concludes that management is a series of activities that includes planning, organizing, mobilizing, controlling, and evaluating which are implemented in the activities of an organization in order to realize the goals and objectives of the organization. And in relation to managing certification in improving the efficiency of education services in madrasas, it is an activity to plan, organize, mobilize, supervise, and evaluate all activities in the organization in order to improve education services in madrasas.

3.4. Educational Services

Service is the key to success in a variety of businesses or activities that are services. According to Moenir, service is "the process of fulfilling needs through other people's direct activities".⁴⁰ Moenir further stated that service is a process of fulfilling needs through other people's activities that are carried out directly. The service is essentially a series of activities, because the service is a process, then the service takes place routinely and continuously covering the entire life of people in the community. Service delivery can be measured, therefore standards can be set in either the time required or the results. According to Sinambela's public service in his book *Public Service Reform, Theory, Policy, and Implementation* is that public service can be defined as the provision of services (serving) the needs of people or people who have an interest in the organization in accordance with the basic rules and procedures that have been set.⁴¹ Endang Wiryatmi stated that: "Public service is something that is provided either by government or private organizations, because the community in general cannot meet these needs themselves except through the collective."⁴²

³⁶E. Mulyasa, *Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah: Konsep, Strategi, dan Implementasi*, (Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya, 2003), cet. Ke- 5, hlm. 19

³⁷Syaiful Sagala, *Manajemen Strategik dalam Peningkatan Mutu Pendidikan*, (Bandung: CV. ALFABETA, 2010), cet. Ke- 4, hlm. 49

³⁸Syaiful Sagala., *Ibid*, hlm. 51-52

³⁹<http://id.shvoong.com/writing-and-speaking/presenting/2108155-pengertian-pengelolaan/#ixzz2NTNkbVwU>. Diakses 19 Agustus 2016

⁴⁰H.A.S. Moenir, *Manajemen Pelayanan Umum di Indonesia*, (Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2006), hlm. 17

⁴¹Lijan Poltak Sinambela, *Reformasi Pelayanan Publik:Teori, Kebijakan, dan Implementasi*, (Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara, 2007), hlm. 5

⁴²Endang Tri L Wiryatmi, *Manajemen Pelayanan Umum*, (Bandung: LAN, 1996), hlm. 7

Several experts explained about public services, Dwiyanto said public service is a series of activities carried out by public bureaucracy to meet the needs of the community.⁴³ Moenir, public services are: activities carried out by a person or group of people on the basis of material factors through certain systems, procedures and methods in order to meet the interests of others in accordance with their rights. Juniarso Ridwan and Achmad Sodik Sudarajat said that public services are services provided by the Government of the State of the government to its people in order to meet the needs of the community itself and have the aim to improve the welfare of the community. Moenir believes that the government in providing the best service to the public can be done by: 1. Providing ease in handling matters that are considered important. 2. provide reasonable services. 3. give the same treatment without favoritism. 4. be honest and straightforward.⁴⁴

Educational services are included in the categorization of public services where educational services can be interpreted as simply with educational services. The word service (service) itself has several meanings, ranging from personal service (personal service) to the service as a product.⁴⁵ Kotler in the *Integrated Services Management* book defines services as any actions or activities that can be offered to other parties which are basically intangible and do not result in any ownership, the production of services may be related to physical products or vice versa.⁴⁶ Services in educational activities are all activities related to education that prioritize services in the process. Services offered by institutions can be improved through the quality of service elements. Educational institutions are organizations that provide services to internal and external stakeholders. Internal stakeholders consist of all institutions within the school (such as foundations, study programs, and student activity units) and the actors within it (such as students, teachers, business administration, and other staff). External stakeholders consist of alumni, parents of government students and the general public. School success is measured by the level of customer satisfaction, both internal and external. Schools are said to be successful if they are able to provide the same service or exceed customer expectations, because they have issued butged enough in educational institutions.

There are two forms of service in educational institutions, including the following: 1. Basic services, in these basic services are intended to meet the needs of students associated with student services at school, in carrying out their duties the headmaster is assisted by school professional personnel employed in the system schools include teaching service personnel, administrative service personnel, school facility service personnel, student or student service personnel. 2. Assist services, these services are needed because of the rapid changes in the dynamics of society as experienced today, especially in the era of digitalization, these assistance services in the form of library services, school building and yard services, and health and security services. In addition there are also services in the field of guidance and counseling contained in four main service programs, namely: collection services, extension services, information and placement services as well as research and assessment services.⁴⁷ According to Marzuki Mahmud, in general there are

⁴³Agus Dwiyanto, *Mewujudkan Good Governance Melalui Pelayanan Publik*, (Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press, 2005), hlm. 141

⁴⁴H.A.S. Moenir, *Ibid.*, hlm. 4

⁴⁵Rambat Lupiyadi dan A. Hamdani, *Manajemen Pemasaran Jasa*, (Jakarta: Salemba Empat, ed II, 2006) hal : 5

⁴⁶M.N. Nasution, *Manajemen Jasa Terpadu*, (Bogor: Ghalia Indonesi, 2004), hlm. 6

⁴⁷M. Sulthon Masyhudi, *Manajemen Pondok Pesantren*, (Jakarta: Diva Pustaka, 2005), hlm. 139

5 education services, namely information services, facilities and infrastructure services, administrative services, guidance services, talent and interest development services and skills, and welfare services.⁴⁸

Based on the explanation above, it can be interpreted that, service is an activity carried out by a government agency or company related to this matter to the public or customers who aim to satisfy it. The context in the level of government agencies, then the service has become the main task that must be given apparatus in order to prosper the community as it should.

4. Research Methodology

This research is a field research using a qualitative research approach. The main focus of this research is the issue of managing certification in improving education services in madrasas. In accordance with the nature and characteristics of qualitative research, this research produces data that reconstructs speech, and the behavior of people or subjects of study. According to Bodgan and Taylor as quoted by Lexy Moeleong, who defines qualitative methodology as a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or oral words from people and observed behavior.⁴⁹

The setting of this study focused on several Aliyah State Madrasas in Jambi Province by accommodating the representation of each region in three categories, namely the western, central, and eastern regions. Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Bangko fulfills representation in the western region, while Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 3 Jambi city represents the central region, while Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat fulfills representation in the eastern region. The selection of this setting is based on rational, practical, and economic considerations that some Madrasah Aliyah Negeri with representation in each region are formal educational institutions owned by the government in this case the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia. The research subjects that were the focus of this study were the madrasah headmasters and teachers who had received certification support.

The types of data in this study are 1. Primary data in the form of data obtained or collected directly from the first source,⁵⁰ 2. Secondary data is data obtained or collected by people conducting research in the field of research from sources that already exist and are included in second source category.⁵¹ This data is usually obtained from libraries or from previous research reports, such as the organizational structure of madrasah development which consists of Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Bangko, Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 3 Jambi city, and Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Kuala Tungkal Tanjung Jabung Barat District.⁵²

⁴⁸Marzuki Mahmud, *Manajemen Mutu Perguruan Tinggi*, (Jakarta: PT RajaGrafindo Persada, 2012), hlm. 63-65

⁴⁹Lexy Moeleong, *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif*, (Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya, 2005), cet. ke-21, hlm. 4

⁵⁰Sumardi Suryabrata, *Metodologi Penelitian*, (Jakarta: PT. RajaGrafindo Persada, 2010), hlm.39

⁵¹Sayid Syekh, *Pengantar Statistik Ekonomi Dan Sosial*, (Jakarta: Gaung Persada Press Jakarta, 2011), hlm. 5. Baca juga Suharsimi Arikunto, *Prosedur Penelitian: Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*, (Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2010), edisi revisi, hlm. 183

⁵²Sayid Syekh, *Pengantar Statistik Ekonomi Dan Sosial*, (Jakarta: Gaung Persada Press Jakarta, 2011), hlm. 5. Baca juga Suharsimi Arikunto, *Prosedur Penelitian: Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*, (Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2010), edisi revisi, hlm. 183

The instruments used to obtain data in this study were participant observation, interviews and documentation studies.⁵³ Analysis of the data used in this study is the analysis of flow data models.⁵⁴ According to Suharsimi Arikunto, data analysis procedures generally go through three steps, namely preparation, tabulation, and application of data in accordance with the research approach. Data analysis techniques that will be carried out are 1. reducing data, 2. presenting data, and concluding data.⁵⁵

The examination technique used in this study is based on one criterion, namely credibility. Credibility standards are needed so that the results of qualitative research can be trusted by readers and can be approved by the participants studied. With this need, there are four data checks used in this study, namely: 1. extension of participation, 2. persistence of observation and triangulation of data.⁵⁶

5. Research Findings and Analysis of Research Results

Based on the data and research facts that the author found in the research field through interviews, observations, and documentation, it will be comprehensively described in the next discussion. The discussion and analysis of the data is expected to be able to provide answers to some of the problems that are the study and discussion of this study

5.1. Effectiveness of Teacher Certification in Improving Teacher Professional Services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province

The study of the effectiveness of teacher certification is rooted in three basic things, namely input, process, and output which then accommodates all procedures and processes so that a teacher in his capacity as an educator in a madrasa is declared legally and convincingly based on the applicable laws and regulations as a professional teaching staff and therefore entitled to receive additional allowances from the government which is then called the teacher professional allowance. To obtain accurate data and information related to the problems that have been explained before, the following authors describe partially based on the reality that occurs in each Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province

Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Merangin Procedure for Recruitment of Teacher Certification Candidates

This madrasa is one of the first public madrasahs in Merangin Regency, Jambi Province with 32 teachers, both civil servants and honorary staff. Specifically, there are 20 teachers who have received professional teacher allowances, including the headmaster of the madrasa.

The effectiveness of teacher certification in relation to teacher professional services carried out is inseparable from the procedures and processes of issuing teacher certificates which are a basic

⁵³Suharsimi Arikunto, *Prosedur Penelitian: Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*, (Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2010), edisi revisi, hlm. 198

⁵⁴Suharsimi Arikunto, *Op.Cit.*, hlm. 278

⁵⁵Matthew B. Miles and Michael Huberman, *Qualitative Data Analysis*, (London-New Delhi: SAGA Publication, 1994), edisi ke- 2, hlm. 10

⁵⁶Lexy J. Moleong, *Op.Cit.*, hlm. 330

element in the submission of candidates for teacher professional support (TPG) in the Madrasah Activity and Budget Plan (RKAM). Issuance of certificates has gone through a series of formal activities that must be followed by each prospective beneficiary, then formulated with the input, process and output categories. Furthermore according to him that what is meant by input is the initial process of recruiting prospective candidates for the teacher professional allowance which at the beginning of the process is more administrative in nature. Where each teacher with certain terms of service is given the opportunity to collect several documents in accordance with the implementation instructions (operational guidelines) and technical instructions (technical guidelines) to then be analyzed and evaluated by the team determined by the government. After the portfolio process is completed, the Team then submits the results of studies and assessments that provide information related to teachers who have passed the portfolio selection and are declared entitled to obtain teacher certification and with all matters related to the certificate, including the right to pay allowances teacher profession (certification).

After a number of years the certification process took place, the government then conducted various studies related to the new formulation in the process of recruiting prospective teachers' professional allowance candidates, which until now is known as Teacher Training and Education (PLPG). The problem then arises when the recruitment procedure for prospective teachers receiving professional allowance is only administrative in nature, where teachers who are in certain categories according to specified conditions are only charged to fulfill administrative documents. So then they can carry out various data manipulations to meet the achievement targets set forth in the assessment criteria determined by the government formed Team, in this case several universities appointed to conduct verification and assessment of the teacher portfolio. This process then becomes an important indicator that the initial process of recruiting prospective teacher professional allowances (certification) has not yet led to enhancing teacher professionalism, so they then assume that the implications of these activities are more directed towards improving teacher welfare.

Weak Implementation of Government Regulations Regarding Discipline of Civil Servants

The problem that often arises in madrasahs in the context of teaching and learning activities is the enforcement of disciplines that have not been optimal due to various factors, both internal and external. The existence of a madrasah head as a top manager in principle is an extension of the government in managing the organization of educational institutions which in this case are madrasahs. The logical consequence of this position is that every madrasah head must implement the Laws and Government Regulations that have been determined previously. But then the problem is that not all madrasah principals have professional and proportional competence in overcoming various problems related to disciplinary enforcement in madrasahs. The weakness that has been experienced is disciplining all assemblies of teachers and employees, especially certified teachers. Weaknesses in the implementation of teacher discipline will arise when the problems faced are in contact with senior teachers who historically have long dedicated their knowledge in teaching and learning activities, especially in MAN 1 Merangin Jambi Province.

Based on the above data explanation, the writer can conclude that the effectiveness of teacher certification is not yet capable in improving teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Merangin Jambi Province due to two basic factors, namely the recruitment procedure for teacher certification candidates and the weak implementation of government regulations on

discipline Civil Servants (PNS). The process and procedure for the recruitment of teacher certification candidates at the beginning of its implementation through the portfolio channel resulted in the emergence of negative assumptions among teachers, especially in MAN 1 Merangin, so they then assumed that the provision of certification allowance was more than a government effort to improve the quality of teacher welfare without having to think about feedback contributive in improving the quality and competency quality of each certified teacher. In addition, the inconsistency of madrasa principals in enforcing government regulations on the discipline of Civil Servants (PNS) has direct and indirect implications for the process of implementing teaching and learning activities in madrasas.

Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 3 Kota Jambi

Disbursement of certification allowances in MAN 3 Jambi City is distributed every month after all the requirements as stipulated in the technical guidelines (technical guidelines) and implementation guidelines (operational guidelines) for disbursement of professional allowances have been met by certified teachers. Furthermore according to him, that the madrasa in relation to the administration of professional teacher allowance distribution will not change the pattern of the current disbursement system that has been in effect in accordance with the expectations of the entire teacher assembly. However, according to him, in relation to the effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services in MAN 3, the city of Jambi was more dominant in the distribution of these allowances. In the sense of the word that administratively, madrasas have provided professional teacher allowance which is the right of each certified teacher. However, the problem is that the positive effects of the provision of these allowances have not been able to improve the services of the teaching profession, especially in MAN 3 Jambi city, which leads to three basic things, namely the character of teachers, binding regulations, and limited educational facilities.

Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat

The fundamental issue of the effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services actually has very diverse differences among educational practitioners in various educational institutions, especially Madrasah Aliyah Negeri in Jambi Province. When the same problem is then raised to several state madrasas, it automatically has different assumptions in response to the problems raised. It can be understood that each educational institution has different stakeholders with different management patterns. This is also the case in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat, where the madrasa is positioned in the context of this study as a research location representing the eastern region. Information about certified teachers can then provide supporting data in analyzing the fundamental reasons why the effectiveness of teacher certification has not been able to improve teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat, Jambi Province.

Teacher certification has not been effective in improving teacher professional services at MAN 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat, especially in relation to the teaching and learning process due to two fundamental factors which later became important indicators, namely the procedure for disbursement of certification allowances and self-actualization.

5.2. Efektifitas Sertifikasi Guru di Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Provinsi Jambi

Teacher certification is considered effective as long as the previously formulated targets can be realized so that they can realistically improve the quality and quality of public service which in this case are activities related to teaching and learning activities in madrasahs. Although textually not included in the implementation instructions (operational guidelines) and technical instructions (technical guidelines) about the feed back from the teacher professional allowance, there is at least a constructive expectation about how to improve the quality and quality of education services provided, especially in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri in Jambi Province. To see comprehensively about the reality of teacher certification in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri in Jambi Province, this section will present an analysis of the effectiveness of certification in various Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province.

Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Merangin

Administratively the management of teacher certification in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Merangin Jambi Province is quite effective with the main indicators that all digital administration procedures are in accordance with operational guidelines and technical guidelines for disbursing teacher professional allowance for fiscal year 2018. These indications can be seen from several SIMPATICS features of MAN teachers 1 Merangin has reached the SKAKPT level which also means that the head of the madrasah as the authority of the budget user is not obliged to distribute the teacher's professional allowance.

Thus, all certified teachers in the madrasahs are given a certification allowance in accordance with the nominal salary of each teacher. The effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services in principle requires the achievement of three important components of the management of educational institutions, namely how the management of teacher certification is well programmed according to applicable operational operating standards, how also the implementation process, and the benefits derived from the teacher certification , both personal and institutional benefits, in this case, are improving the quality and quality of education services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri in Jambi Province, particularly MAN 1 Merangin. An activity can be said to be effective if it is able to implement the three things above, including in the management of educational institutions such as madrasahs and other educational institutions that are characterized by Islam.

Re-discuss the phenomenon that occurs in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Merangin in relation to the effectiveness of teacher certification. The author can explain concretely that the reality cannot be categorized as a concept that leads to effectiveness because the activity only works well on the administrative aspects. Meanwhile, at the implementation level, it has not been able to have a positive impact and influence in improving teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Merangin. Thus, it can be concluded that there is mismanagement between input, process, and output of activities in relation to the implementation of teacher certification. To provide an overview of the reality mentioned above, the following is shown a conceptual map of the image of the pattern of input relations, processes, and outputs in managing certification.

Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 3 Kota Jambi

The effectiveness of teacher certification in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 3 Jambi city is basically a managerial discourse that leads to how the madrasa head plays his role as the top leader in the effort to actualize management principles, especially related to the distribution of certification allowances for teachers who have educator certificates. According to information from several certified teachers in madrasa administratively all MAN 3 teachers in Jambi City that are licensed by educators have completed their teacher's PTK verbal through SIMPATIKA, starting to activate themselves every semester, updating personal data, digital print out roster, and publishing SKAKPT as the final part of the whole series of drafting of documents in the context of disbursement of certification allowances. They argue that the documents that have been compiled and then submitted by certified teachers to the headmaster of the madrasa cq. The head of administrative affairs is in accordance with the operational and technical guidelines set by the government.

Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat

Based on some information that has been obtained previously, the author can explain that administratively, the management of teacher certification in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat is quite effective, which is marked by the complete documentation of the disbursement requirements for the certification allowance. However, the effectiveness is only directed at the administrative level, while the expected progressive impact in the context of improving the quality and quality of the teaching professional services at MAN 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat has not been able to make a significant contribution. This is consistent with the information conveyed by several certified teachers that so far there has not been a significant change in the distribution of the certification allowance, both before rolling the allowance and post-distribution in the context of increasing professionalism such as innovation in learning, work productivity and other productive activities.

5.3. Teacher Professional Services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province

Teacher professional services in the context of management of teacher certification allowance management are fundamental aspects in the management of education in general. The capacity of teachers and education personnel in madrasas is an important component that cannot be ignored, so that all madrasa principals must have accurate management patterns and capability so that they are able to implement management principles in madrasah institutional organizations. It should be further discussed whether the placement of each madrasa head is in accordance with the recruitment of the head, or only based on the principle of filling in the gaps. This issue is basically the authority of the policy maker (decision maker) as regulated in government regulations. However, good management of certification is in accordance with procedures in an effort to improve education services back to two important aspects, namely administrative management and personnel management.

5.4. Effectiveness of Teacher Certification in Improving Teacher Professional Services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province

The effectiveness of teacher certification is a concept that implies that teacher certification will be effective if it meets at least three important criteria, namely programs, processes, and outputs.

Related to the teacher certification program, the authors can point out that the program is a national program and has been through various discussions from experts, both economists in relation to education budgeting, education experts as observers of the conceptions of education implementation, education politicians as legislators in determine the direction of national education, and other parties directly related to the program.

This section is an important and integrated part of the discussion that has been presented previously, so that later discussion also accommodates the findings obtained from the analysis of previous data. The discussion in this section will focus on certain aspects that lead to factors that can inhibit the improvement of the quality of the teaching profession services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province.

As explained in the previous discussion, the focus of this research study is the management of education services after the distribution of teacher professional allowance to the Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province in improving the quality and quality of education services and various factors that have direct and indirect implications for these education services, as well as measures constructive steps in improving the quality and quality of services in the teaching and learning process. On the basis of some of the above criteria, then in this section the author will present an in-depth analysis related to some of the things that have been stated previously.

Every activity held in madrasahs, both included in the intracurricular and extracurricular categories, is inseparable from deficiencies, so continuous improvements are needed to have a positive impact on the overall education process in madrasahs. Likewise, with the education services provided at madrasahs, both by teachers and education personnel, as well as the madrasah head as the top leader in the institution. Related to the factors that can influence education services in madrasahs, in principle depends on one's perspective. The factors which are then considered to have a direct and indirect impact on the services of educators in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri in Jambi Province can be categorized into two basic things, namely internal factors, external factors. The initial assumption was built on the results of the author's observations in the research field by observing several Aliyah State Madrasahs in Jambi Province. The initial observation phase was conducted at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Merangin by observing what factors were then considered to have an impact on educational services at the madrasah. Likewise, when the observations were continued at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 3 Jambi city, the problems found in the research field had similarities in accordance with the characteristics and focus of the study. And the latest observation was conducted at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat with a focus on observing the factors that were considered to have an impact on education services in madrasahs. Based on data obtained from observations in the research field, it can be formulated that the factors that can affect the effectiveness of education services in madrasahs consist of two factors, namely internal factors and external factors.

Analysis of Research Results

The discussion of the extent to which the effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri in Jambi Province is basically an actualization of management principles that have been discussed by management experts concretely which then becomes an important reference in educational services carried out in madrasahs. Therefore, dejure

and defacto must be balanced in order to produce a good process in order to realize optimal results in accordance with the expectations of all education stakeholders.

Although the government does not provide achievement targets in the form of improving professional teaching services related to the intent and purpose of the distribution of the certification allowance, but by looking at the phenomenon that occurs in the field, it is necessary to reconsider various breakthroughs and other alternative businesses, both among education practitioners including those madrasa heads, teachers and education personnel, as well as policy makers who in this case are legislators to then be implemented in real and factual terms by executives who in this case are the government, both the central and regional governments.

The breakthroughs and efforts referred to in this study are not only discourses which then become a source of debate in the public sphere, but need to be actualized in the form of clear regulations and lead to development and improvement in all education sectors, especially educational regulations relating directly to the grass root education. This needs to be considered in depth that ordinary people do not pay much attention to how the distribution of certification allowance is carried out, but rather they look at the results (output) of education. They instead placed greater hopes on the madrasa as an educational institution characterized by Islam to then contribute in improving the quality and quality of its graduates and be able to compete with other graduates from various educational institutions, especially in the face of a global era laden with competition. The discussion in this section focuses more on analyzing some of the findings in the field of research related to the effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province. As for the study of teacher professional services that have not increased optimally can be seen in further discussion.

Teacher Discipline

Madrasas in the historical review experienced development and growth along with the increasing public interest in the cultivation of the characteristics of morality in the students themselves. Growth and development is also supported by administrative services, both online and online. One aspect that seems so clear is that the administration of educators and education personnel has begun to be accommodated online which is connected directly to the Central Ministry of Religion server. So then all information sourced from the Central Ministry of Religion can be accessed directly by all educators and education personnel. Such indicators can be seen for example from each SIMPATIKA madrasa, where all activities of teaching and learning activities of teachers can be updated through the SIMPATIKA program.

Based on the information above it can be understood that technically, educators and education personnel are able to fulfill administrative bills as a prerequisite in obtaining the teacher's professional allowance. However, the real problem lies not only in the administrative management aspect, but an important aspect and the main objective of the provision of these benefits is the improvement of education services in madrasas as feed backs from the provision of the teacher's professional allowances from the government.

Based on some information, there are data and research facts found in the field of research related to education services provided by teachers after the provision of professional teacher allowance is that some teachers in the madrasas still consider that the teacher professional allowance is one of

the government's efforts in improving living standards teacher. The improvement of education services is an effort carried out together in accordance with the capacities and abilities of each teacher. According to the authors that the assumptions built among teachers as explained above, is a misleading of the purpose of the teacher professional allowance, the capacity of the madrasah head as the main manager in developing and improving the quality and quality of education services has not been fully implemented optimally, so implementation is needed the principles of management in totality while continuing to prioritize persuasive approaches with all the limitations possessed by each madrasa head.

Quality of Teaching

The question that often arises among education practitioners is how the quality of teaching teachers after the provision of teacher professional allowances. Akapakah then after the provision of benefits has a significant impact on the quality of education services that they have in the process of teaching and learning activities in madrasas. As previously explained, one of the objectives of the government in the context of the provision of teacher professional allowance is to improve the quality and quality of teaching of teachers in madrasas with various activities that they can do. In the sense that each teacher after obtaining the allowance feels called to improve the quality of their teaching by broadening their horizons and insight into thinking by adding various references and other learning resources, so then the material they convey is more varied and interesting for students. Besides that, they can use some of these benefits in improving their quality in the field of information and technology (IT), and several other constructive steps in developing and improving the competence of each teacher.

As a form of responsibility and logical consequence of the professional teacher allowance, every teacher must have strategic and progressive steps in improving their pedagogical competencies, such as attending education and training related to the teaching profession. But the facts on the ground, often arise in public debates about the low quality and quality of teachers caused by their apathy with various reasons stated. Therefore, to see how the real facts that occur in the field of research in relation to the quality and quality of learning in madrasas in Jambi Province, the authors then make observations in several representative madrassas from the West, Central and East. Associated with the above ideas, the authors then visited Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Banko on effective days with the intention to see how the quality and quality of learning undertaken by teachers after receiving professional teacher allowances. At first the writer observed how the situation of the teaching and learning process activities that were taking place at MAN 1 Merangin, starting from the bell sign of the start of teaching and learning activities at the first hour which is 07.15 WIB.

On the occasion of the observation the author still found several teachers who experienced late entry even though the time was still within normal limits and had little impact on teaching and learning activities. After ascertaining that all teachers were present in the teaching and learning process, the writer began to observe the learning process carried out by the teacher, in this case, having received a professional teacher allowance with the aim of ascertaining whether there was a significant change in the quality of learning carried out after the teacher's professional allowance was rolled out. In these observations, it turns out the authors get data and information that is quite accurate as the assumptions that develop among the general public, where the teacher who is the focus of the writer's observation seems to carry out their duties and responsibilities in the mediocre

category, where the main source of learning used is only Student Worksheets (LKS) using the lecture method, so then the learning activities are quite monotonous and have an impact on the inactivity of the students in the learning activities. And thus means the teacher is still using traditional learning patterns that are more directed at the teacher centered model (teacher-centered learning), without being accompanied by a variety of learning innovations that are expected to increase the attractiveness of students in teaching and learning activities.

On another occasion the author also observed teaching and learning activities in another room in different study hours, this writer did to crosscheck the information that had been obtained previously. The focus of the observations of the authors of this session is basically not much different from before, it's just that observations are more directed to the field of technology in learning activities undertaken by teachers after the teacher professional allowance. This opportunity the authors take advantage of by directly observing aspects of technology that are implemented in teachers in classroom learning. When observations take place, the authors directly observe the activities of teachers who have been certified in the learning room, whether the learning process is carried out using technology, say for example the use of computer media in explaining material in front of the class, because according to technology experts that the use of computer-based media that contains various materials teaching that attracts students in the teaching and learning process. The results of these observations, it turns out that teachers with professional qualifications and licensed as evidenced by educator certificates and accompanied by payment of teacher professional allowances have not been able to apply electronic devices as mentioned earlier, and this is the result of direct interviews with the teacher concerned at which time the authors sought communicate directly with the teacher concerned after the learning activities end. Related to some data obtained from the observations and interviews mentioned above, then the authors argue that meeting the needs of teachers in the financial context which in this case is the provision of teacher professional allowances is one of the government's efforts to improve the quality and quality of education output so that they are able to compete in global world. So then when this reality is seen from the perspective of the needs theory initiated by Abraham H. Maslow who states that a person behaves because it is driven by the desire to obtain fulfillment in various needs. Be it physical needs, safety needs or security needs, group needs, respect needs, and self-fulfillment needs become non-correlative between government bills to teachers who have received the teacher professional allowance with certain tasks exceeding the teacher's main tasks in educational activities in madrasahs.

Apart from the problem of meeting the needs of teachers in the context of teacher professional allowance, principals of madrasahs in principle have significant space and time in the management of teachers after the provision of professional teacher allowances. The headmaster of the madrasah as a leader has managerial capacity both in terms of administration and human resources for teachers after the teacher professional allowance. To see the extent of the role of the madrasah head in improving managerial aspects in efforts to improve education services in the madrasah, the authors directly interviewed the madrasah head MAN 1 Merangin who represented the western region, the madrasah head MAN 3 Jambi city representing the central region, and the madrasah head MAN 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat as a representation of the eastern region at a different time from a structured interview pattern in relation to the management of teachers and education personnel in improving education services in madrasahs.

According to the head of MAN 1 Merangin that the arrangement of certified teachers with the support of professional teacher allowances has been well managed from an administrative aspect, where in the administration section a special staff has been directly appointed to manage the administration of completing the requirements for disbursement of certification, both online and non online so then in terms of updating data on the online service never experience delays such as updating attendance at SIMPATIKA, activating collectively in each semester, and even on publishing SKAKPT online which is the final completeness in the implementation instructions (operational guidelines) and technical implementation instructions (technical guidelines) in the disbursement of teacher professional allowances every semester. Likewise, as stated by the head of MAN 3 in the city of Jambi, that the real problem in relation to the requirements for disbursement of teacher professional allowance is not in the administrative management aspect as mentioned earlier, he said that every year the teacher professional teacher allowance at the Director General of GTK Ministry of Religion The center has formulated and distributed openly online and can be accessed by all teachers and education staff in connection with the operational guidelines and technical guidelines for disbursing teacher professional allowances each school year, so that they are then able to facilitate teachers in meeting administrative requirements in disbursing teacher professional allowances. The same thing was also conveyed by the head of MAN 1 Tanjung Jabung Barat that the administration of teacher administration as stipulated in the operational guidelines and technical guidelines for disbursing teacher professional allowances did not experience significant obstacles in the sense of the word that the Central Ministry of Religion, in this case the Director General of GTK, has provided sufficient access it is easy for all teachers to later verify the data online, although in principle they must be personally resolved by each teacher, but at the discretion of the madrasah head the technical problems can be resolved by technical personnel appointed by the madrasah head, so that the data Factual from the teacher can be accommodated in SIMPATIKA as the main media of the Director General of GTK in seeing how the development of teachers in the administrative aspects of the management of teacher professional allowances.

As explained earlier that the headmaster of MAN 1 Merangin madrasah, MAN 3 of Jambi city, and MAN 1 of Tanjung Jabung Barat have the same perception that administratively the management of teacher professional allowances has not yet found significant obstacles in fulfilling teacher rights in the payment of teacher professional allowances. The problem that then arises is how then personally teachers with professional teacher allowance are able to improve their pedagogical competencies, both in the aspects of classroom management, self-discipline, learning innovation, and the loyalty of each teacher in helping students develop academic and non-academic potential. academically, so that after they finish their education at the madrasa, they will have proportional competencies in accordance with the characteristics of the madrasah's vision and mission as previously formulated.

Based on research data obtained through interviews, the main factor limiting teachers in improving education services in madrasas lies not in the administrative management aspect, but the real problem lies in each teacher. Madrasah principals are aware that they have limitations in terms of imposing sanctions that are heavy, because indeed in each madrasa has rules and regulations which then become a reference in overall madrasa management. In each madrasa it has been formulated that the applicable provisions have three categories of violations which are accompanied by three sanctions, namely minor violations, moderate violations, and serious violations. Similarly

sanctions, ranging from minor sanctions in the form of verbal and written reprimands, moderate sanctions in the form of submission of a motion of no confidence, and severe sanctions that lead to the dismissal of civil servants as stipulated in Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia number 53 of 2010 concerning Discipline of Civil Servants and the Law Republic of Indonesia number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers.

Against the forms of sanctions as explained previously, that each madrasa head was only able to implement light sanctions in the form of verbal and written reprimands for teachers who in fact did not carry out their duties and responsibilities as stipulated in the Teacher and Lecturer Law and Government Regulations number 53 of 2010 above. The acknowledgment of each madrasa head that they have never been given a moderate sanction in the form of demotion and rank is lower than the previous rank and class of teachers who are considered disciplinary and not in accordance with the spirit of the legislation mentioned above. According to them, this is a procedure beyond their capacity as head of madrasa, and automatically requires a considerable amount of time with administrative completeness as evidence of non-compliance with regulations established by the government.

Based on the explanation above, the authors see that the approach used by each madrasa head is more directed to a personal approach that is persuasive by promoting the values of brotherhood and togetherness in building a madrasa in a better direction. However, the nuance will be different when this issue has become a tradition and a habit in the madrasa. Where teachers who have obtained professional allowances for certain reasons then do not carry out their duties and responsibilities in accordance with existing procedures, and then have a negative precedent on themselves that the headmaster as an ordinary teacher who is given additional duties as headmaster, will not be able to impose severe sanctions which then leads to the dismissal and / or transfer of teachers to certain areas which are in the form of indirect sanctions. Thus, the above indicator is one of the factors that in the author's view why after the granting of professional teacher benefits has not been able to improve education services in madrasahs.

6. Conclusions

Based on the explanation in the previous discussion, the authors formulated some conclusions which are the findings in this study. The conclusions in this study are as follows: 1. Effectiveness of teacher certification in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province has not been able to optimally improve teacher professional service due to inconsistent recruitment procedures for teacher certification candidates, weak implementation of government regulations on PNS discipline, no regulations have been found that bind certified teachers, and the actualization is not yet optimal certified teacher. 2. The effectiveness of teacher certification in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province has not been implemented properly due to the operational guidelines and technical certification guidelines that only lead to fulfilling administrative obligations and have not touched on the impact and results of the teacher professional allowance. 3. Teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi Province prioritize the fulfillment of non-substantive aspects such as efforts to fulfill obligations which then give birth to the rule "براءة من الذمة" without consideration of making various creative breakthroughs and innovations. 4. The effectiveness of teacher certification in improving teacher professional services in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Jambi

Province is more pragmatic. So that certified teachers are more concerned with meeting economic needs rather than updating in the teaching and learning process.

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